

Results of Content Validity Index (CVI)

Content Validity Index (CVI) for Waste Management Survey

Construct	Sub-Construct	Item No.	Item	Expert Ratings (1–4)	I-CVI	Decision
Waste Management Practices	Reduce	1	I choose products with little or no plastic packaging.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		2	I avoid buying things that I do not really need.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		3	I make an effort to consume all the food so that nothing is wasted.	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I prioritize using products sold in bulk rather than individually packaged ones.	2, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		5	I show others the proper ways to reduce the use of plastic and paper.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	1.00	Excellent
Waste Management Practices	Reuse	1	I use my own containers (tumbler, lunch box, eco bag) instead of disposable ones.	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I keep bottles, jars, or boxes so they can be reused.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		3	I repurpose old items (e.g., old clothes as cleaning rags).	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		4	I allow my family to reuse items instead of throwing them away immediately.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I show others the benefits of reusing items.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	1.00	Excellent
Waste Management Practices	Recycle	1	I segregate biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and recyclable waste.	4, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I participate in or support recycling programs in the barangay or school.	3, 3, 2	1.00	Retain
		3	I create simple recycled crafts (e.g., plant pots made from bottles).	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I give bottles, cans, and paper that can still be recycled to junk shops.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I take part in school or barangay activities that promote recycling awareness.	2, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	1.00	Excellent
Waste Management Practices	Recover / Dispose	1	I dispose of waste at the proper time and in the designated containers.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain

		2	I use the barangay's designated Materials Recovery Facility (MRF).	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		3	I practice composting of biodegradable waste (if space is available).	3, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I ensure that no waste is thrown into canals, roads, or rivers.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I follow the barangay's "No Segregation, No Collection" policy.	3, 2, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	1.00	Excellent

CVI for Eco-Guilt (All Sub-Constructs)

Construct	Sub-Construct	Item No.	Item	Expert Ratings (1–4)	I-CVI	Decision
Eco-Guilt	Emotional Discomfort	1	I feel guilty when I do not properly segregate my household waste.	4, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I feel guilty when I use more plastic than necessary.	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		3	I feel guilty when I engage in behaviors that contribute to littering.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		4	I feel guilty when I do not follow proper waste disposal practices.	3, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
		5	I feel guilty when I fail to fulfill my responsibility in proper waste management.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	0.93	Excellent
Eco-Guilt	Awareness of Consequences	1	I recognize that disposing of waste improperly can seriously harm human health.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		2	I am aware that poor waste management significantly damages the environment.	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		3	I understand that throwing garbage into rivers or canals contributes to flooding.	4, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I am concerned about the potential impact of poor waste management on future generations.	4, 4, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I take into account the negative effects on my community when I fail to segregate waste properly.	3, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	1.00	Excellent
Eco-Guilt	Moral Accountability	1	I believe it is my responsibility to manage my waste properly.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		2	I think it is wrong not to contribute to proper waste management.	4, 4, 4	1.00	Retain
		3	I feel accountable when I fail to follow proper waste disposal practices.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain

		4	I consider it my obligation to demonstrate correct waste management behavior.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I believe I should take action when I see improper waste disposal.	3, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	0.93	Excellent
Eco-Guilt	Social Pressure Guilt	1	I feel uneasy when others see me disposing of waste improperly.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I feel embarrassed when neighbors criticize me for improper waste practices.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		3	My reputation is affected when I do not follow the 4Rs.	2, 3, 3	0.67	Revise
		4	I worry that others will respect me less if they see me littering.	3, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
		5	I feel ashamed in front of my family or friends when I neglect cleanliness.	2, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	0.73	Needs revision

CVI for Eco-Responsibility

Construct	Sub-Construct	Item No.	Item	Expert Ratings (1–4)	I-CVI	Decision
Eco-Responsibility	Sense of Moral Duty	1	I consider it my duty to protect the environment through proper waste management.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		2	I regard following the 4Rs as a moral obligation.	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		3	Being responsible for waste is part of who I am.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		4	I believe it is wrong not to support the community's cleanliness programs.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I see it as my responsibility to teach others proper waste management practices.	3, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	0.93	Excellent
Eco-Responsibility	Proactive Commitment	1	I voluntarily participate in the community's cleanliness programs.	4, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I do not wait for others before properly disposing of waste.	4, 4, 3	1.00	Retain
		3	I take steps to reduce waste even without being instructed.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I personally take the initiative to recycle or reuse materials.	4, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		5	I offer suggestions on how to improve waste management in the community.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	1.00	Excellent

Eco-Responsibility	Community Accountability	1	I believe I have a responsibility to my community regarding waste management.	4, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I participate in community or school clean-up drives.	3, 3, 2	0.67	Revise
		3	I help neighbors understand the importance of waste segregation.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I encourage my family and friends to be responsible with waste.	3, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
		5	I see myself as part of the solution to my community's waste problems.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	0.87	Good
Eco-Responsibility	Consistency of Behavior	1	I consistently practice waste segregation.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		2	I am disciplined in disposing of waste properly wherever I am.	3, 3, 4	1.00	Retain
		3	Even when busy, I make sure to follow proper waste disposal practices.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
		4	I consistently follow the community's waste management policies.	3, 2, 3	0.67	Revise
		5	I maintain good waste management habits even when no one is watching.	3, 3, 3	1.00	Retain
	S-CVI/Ave	–	–	–	0.93	Excellent